

Food Safety in Community Food Organisations:

Understanding the Challenges in Yorkshire

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Glossary and information

CFO: Community Food Organisation

CLD: Causal Loop Diagram

CS: CFO Case Study

FSA: Food Standards Agency

NGO: Non-Governmental Organisation

PCSOs: Police Community Support Officers

PPDS: Prepacked for Direct Sale

SFBB: Safer Food, Better Business

SOP: Standard Operating Procedure

SP: Supermarket Case Study

WRAP: The Waste and Resources Action Programme

FareShare: The UK's national network of charitable food redistributors, made up of 18 independent organisations. They redistribute surplus food from supermarkets, restaurants, and local providers to nearly 8,000 frontline charities and community groups [6].

Food Standards Agency (FSA): An independent government department protecting public health and consumer interests by ensuring food safety, providing scientific and policy advice, and enforcing food regulations across England, Wales, and Northern Ireland [7].

Waste & Resources Action Programme (WRAP): A global environmental Non Governmental Organisation (NGO) that promotes circular living by designing practical, evidence-based solutions to reduce waste, cut emissions, and transform food, product, and textile systems for the benefit of people, nature, and the climate [8].

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1. Executive Summary

This report examines the challenges Community Food Organisations (CFOs) face in maintaining food safety and hygiene while redistributing surplus food and provides recommendations to strengthen the current system. It was produced through the GenerationResearch scheme in collaboration with FixOurFood, FareShare Yorkshire, and the Food Standards Agency (FSA). The study builds on the FSA's earlier qualitative research into CFOs' experiences with food safety. It reviews guidance from the FSA, FareShare, and WRAP, and develops policy recommendations based on interviews with nine CFOs and one UK supermarket.

The findings show that CFOs play an important role in reducing food waste and improving access to safe and nutritious food. At the same time, they experience several operational and compliance challenges, including:

- Inconsistent CFO approval processes across suppliers
- Limited facilities for repackaging and labelling loose goods
- Volunteer turnover and availability with reliance on experienced staff
- Uncertainty around best freezing practices and timelines
- Unfamiliarity with certain surplus food items
- Limited awareness of available food safety guidance and training

The following actions are recommended:

- Establish clear expectations between CFOs and suppliers, and standardise safety compliance agreements
- Provide labels and packaging for safe bulk food redistribution
- Clarify freezing guidance, including recommended timelines for safe freezing
- Develop welcome packs with recommended training and visual guidance such as checklists and top tips as a neutral supporting resource
- Provide recipes to support the use of unfamiliar items
- Raise public awareness of surplus food redistribution and its benefits
- Increase funding opportunities and awareness of them to cover staff, training, and essential equipment and support in applying for them

In conclusion, CFOs are vital in addressing food insecurity and building community, yet they continue to face barriers in meeting food safety standards and managing surplus food. Progress depends on setting clear expectations for CFOs and suppliers, introducing consistent processes for compliance, and providing accessible training and tools. With this support, CFOs will be better placed to apply safe practices reliably, strengthening both community benefit and the long-term sustainability of surplus food redistribution.

2. Background

Community Food Organisations (CFOs), including food banks, pantries, community cafés and co-operatives, have expanded significantly over the past decade in response to the cost-of-living crisis and gaps in welfare provision. Limited income support through policies such as Universal Credit and under resourced local schemes has driven growing demand. CFO networks estimate that more than 6,300 organisations now operate across the UK, providing access to food support [1]. Despite this growth, many in the sector emphasise that food aid should not be a primary form of support.

Whenever I get asked what our long term aims for funding are – our long-term aim is for us not to exist, because I don't think we should have to. (CS1)

The growth of the Trussell Trust network and emergency food parcel distribution presented in Figure 1 has been linked to the cost of living crisis and an inadequate welfare system [2]. The FSA's Consumer Insights Tracker found that 21% of people aged 16 and over reported being worried about affording food in March 2025 [3]. While this represents a gradual decline from 28% in July 2023, concerns about food affordability remain widespread and contribute to the continued reliance on CFOs.

Low-cost trading models, such as pantries, have grown alongside direct payments to families facing hardship. Many CFOs now provide additional services, such as welfare advice offered directly, through referrals, or by signposting. Campaigning and policy advocacy at both local and national levels has also expanded [1], highlighting the need for systemic change.

FareShare Yorkshire is a regional centre part of FareShare the UK's national surplus food distribution network who deliver food support to over 400 CFOs. They source food from manufacturers, processors, retailers and more recently directly from farmers. FareShare Yorkshire have recently opened the FullCrumb Kitchen, a training and development kitchen aiming to help individuals from CFOs improve their cooking skills whilst applying key food safety principles from the Level 2 Food Safety and Hygiene Training.

Figure 1. Number of emergency food parcels distributed by food banks in the Trussell Trust network [10].

2. Background

2.1 FSA's Qualitative Research [2]

The FSA carried out qualitative research with eight CFOs to examine their approaches to food safety, sourcing and training, to identify challenges and potential support the FSA could provide.

Table 1. Summary of challenges faced by CFOs.

Challenge	Current CFO practices	Suggested FSA support
Traceability and allergen management	Accept unpackaged or unlabelled items (e.g. bread, pastries). Label with all 14 allergens when ingredients are unknown, limiting distribution. Some avoid high-risk foods; others use vegetarian-only menus.	Work with donors to provide ingredient and allergen lists ensuring items are labelled, in date and safe. Share accessible labelling approaches.
Use-by and best-before dates	Use visual checks and precautionary decisions, sometimes causing waste. Uncertain safe freezing and post-thaw times. Occasionally receive goods past use-by or unsuitable for redistribution.	Provide clear guidance for food close to or at its use-by date and freezing rules. Develop easy-reference charts and promote upstream measures to prevent unsuitable donations.
Temperature control, storage, and facilities	Use short transport windows, cool bags and scheduling to maintain safe temperatures. Limited cold storage or monitoring equipment. Apply protocols for higher-risk items (e.g. eggs, meat, dairy) or decline them.	Share best practice on simple storage and plastic-free produce handling. Provide visual resources and offer grants or signposting for refrigeration and monitoring equipment.
Volunteer knowledge and confidence	Rely on mentoring, shadowing and targeted training for key roles. Cost and access limit formal training.	Offer free or subsidised Level 1–2 Food Safety and Hygiene Training. Provide on-site coaching and tailored resources for new CFOs.

2. Background

2.2 Causal Loop Diagram (CLD)

CLDs map positive (+) and negative (-) relationships between factors in a system. A CLD presented in Figure 2 was created based on the qualitative research carried out by the FSA investigating CFO's experiences with food safety [2]. The CLD shows how elements influencing food safety in CFOs are connected, highlighting how a change in one area can affect another. CLDs can be used to analyse system behaviour and identify leverage points for effective intervention.

In summary, volunteer confidence is central to food safety. It increases with clear guidance, training and accurate labelling, but is weakened by language barriers or staff turnover. Grant funding helps by providing resources for training, equipment and staff time, which reduce workload and strengthen compliance. Monitoring and regulation also support higher standards, while greater confidence reduces precautionary food waste.

Figure 2. CLD showing factors influencing food safety compliance in CFOs.

3. Methodology

This study combined a review of existing literature, analysis of food safety guidance, and qualitative interviews with nine Yorkshire-based CFOs and a UK-based supermarket food waste team.

The literature review included the Fair Food Futures food insecurity report [1] and the FSA's qualitative research exploring community food provision [2] which informed the development of a Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) mapping factors affecting compliance.

Food safety guidance from WRAP, FareShare, and the FSA was compared to identify differences in emphasis, scope, and specificity, with the purpose of assessing how each supports CFOs in managing surplus food safely.

Nine semi-structured interviews, lasting around 30 minutes, were conducted with CFOs receiving surplus food from FareShare. Questions (Appendix) covered organisational role, food safety practices, use of existing guidance, and requests for further guidance to support compliance. Data was thematically analysed (Figure 3) to identify common challenges and support requests.

A further interview with a UK-based supermarket was conducted focusing on how food safety compliance in the UK's system of surplus food redistribution could be improved from their perspective.

4. Results

4.1 Comparison of Food Safety Guidance for CFOs

Table 2. Comparison of food safety guidance for CFOs.

Category	Fareshare	FSA	WRAP
Overall emphasis	Most detailed operational rules for handling surplus food	Broad, accessible guidance that can be adapted to different contexts	Focus on reducing waste and supporting redistribution, with detailed shelf-life information
Business registration	Registration required if food is regularly handled, prepared, or distributed as an organised activity	Encourages early registration and contact with local authorities, even if food is free	
Training	Formal induction and refresher training with Level 3 qualification required for managers and allergen training compulsory	Requires suitable food safety knowledge but leaves format and level open	Recommends ensuring all staff and volunteers have appropriate hygiene training
Traceability	Sets out clear systems for recording and tracking food, audits and traceability reports		

Table 2 compares the food safety guidance from three sources: FareShare, the FSA and WRAP to assess the coverage in key food safety guidance categories and to better understand CFOs' experiences with food safety guidance.

4. Results

4.1 Comparison of Food Safety Guidance for CFOs

Category	Fareshare	FSA	WRAP
Date marking (use-by and best-before)	Strict rules on use-by and best-before, freezing only under set conditions and extensions only with manufacturer approval	Explains marking, use-by must not be exceeded but best-before can be flexible with checks	Most detailed on product-specific shelf-life and quality checks
Labelling and allergen management	Full ingredient and allergen information required, separation of unlabelled goods and clear allergen training	Practical advice on communicating allergen risks, encouraging conversations with consumers	Emphasis on legal obligations, 14 allergens, and correct labelling, especially when repackaging
Storage and temperature control	Specific limits (e.g. max 30 min out of refrigeration), detailed temperature monitoring and pest control contracts	More flexible, focused on safe consumer-level practice	Advises on safe storage and packaging impacts on shelf-life but without prescriptive limits
Damaged packaging and disposal	Some dented or loose goods only for on-site use and strict disposal rules for unsafe items	Outer damage acceptable if primary pack intact	Outer damage acceptable if primary pack intact with quality checks required

In summary, FareShare sets out the most prescriptive operational rules, especially around freezing, unlabelled goods, storage, audits, and traceability, reflecting its role as a redistribution network with direct compliance responsibilities.

The FSA provides both broad guidance designed to be adapted to different settings and more specific guidance for community cooking and food banks [4].

WRAP's focus is on waste prevention and redistribution, offering the most detailed product-specific advice on best-before dates, shelf-life, and packaging impacts.

4. Results

4.2 Qualitative Data Analysis

The qualitative data collected from the CFOs (Table 4) have been coded into a three-tier structure presented in Figure 3.

The structure moves from first-order codes based on CFO's individual experiences with the surplus food redistribution system to broader second-order codes representing higher level themes, and finally to three aggregate themes: surplus food access and distribution, food safety and compliance plus infrastructure and support.

Figure 3. Qualitative data structure.

The Importance of CFOs

The Maslow Hierarchy of Needs highlights that primary human needs, such as access to food, must be satisfied before individuals can focus on higher-level goals like belonging and self-actualisation [10]. This fundamental link between nourishment and a child's ability to learn, participate, and thrive was clear in one reflection:

We were noticing that our very youngest children were arriving either hungry or eating a bag of Quavers and that was their breakfast. What we know that for our children to succeed, be happy, learn and just be a little bit civilised, they need to not be hungry. We're not blaming parents; this is just circumstances. (CS5)

Besides nourishment, it's about **social infrastructure** (CS5). It's a **hook into belonging** (CS3). Despite living in a highly connected society, many people in the UK still feel distanced from their food and communities.

You know, it's only a sandwich that we're eating but we all sit down and interact, and I that that is something that is very much missed because as families we live very busy lives and even within a family unit, people might eat at different times and not at a table. Cooking together is great; there is a lot of camaraderie amongst the women as well. When we've been cooking together, they've kind of offered support to each other. (CS2)

This sense of togetherness is intentionally cultivated by many CFOs, who create spaces where meals are not just consumed but enjoyed through communal dining which encourages conversation and connection.

For us it's more than the nutritional aspect and helping families save money [...] We also place a big importance on sitting down café style, we all have a knife and a fork, we all have a china plate, we are not wandering round holding burger wraps. I'm not saying there's anything wrong with burger wraps but we are quite clear on the social actions and interactions. We use it as a time to relax, unwind and share stories of the day. (CS5)

A. Surplus Food Distribution

a. Knowledge about surplus food

Awareness of why surplus food becomes available to CFOs is not universal. CS2 explained that it is not always simply excess stock:

It's not always because it is surplus, it's also misprinting and change of branding. Things you don't really think about. (CS2)

CS5 suggested that both children and their parents often do not understand that FareShare is the source of some of their meals, or why using surplus food is beneficial. They proposed clearer public messaging, ideally through social media, to communicate the value of surplus food and address misconceptions, for example:

Did you know that your kid's meal last night came from FareShare and these are the benefits: it saves us money, it saves it going into landfill, it's not rotten food, and it's how we can afford to run our food pantry. (CS5)

Changing perceptions is an important goal. Some CFOs emphasised that surplus food is of the same quality as products purchased in supermarkets, and that food safety ultimately depends on the standards and practices maintained by the organisation.

CS5 also reflected on the opportunity to influence children's understanding of food systems and waste from a young age:

How great that you can influence them... so that by the time they grow up, they're more environmentally aware or take a bigger interest in food production with no waste. (CS5)

b. Surplus food distribution systems

Surplus redistribution systems vary between retailers. Some operate through intermediaries, which CS6 reported can introduce delays and uncertainty, meaning CFOs may not always know in advance whether food will be available for collection on a given day. Direct relationships with local suppliers, such as bakeries, were described as more effective, as they could be arranged to suit the CFO's schedule.

Supermarket donation procedures also differed. In some cases, CFOs were required to take all available items, including those unsuitable for redistribution, which increased waste management needs. Other arrangements involved limiting access to donation baskets to specific days, or setting fixed pick-up times, occasionally in the evening:

When we picked it [the donations] up on an evening, I used to have to bring it back here [charity premises] to sort, to put in the fridge and freezers. (CS6)

CS6 also observed that some suppliers had not visited the organisation to see the impact of their donations. They suggested that such visits could help suppliers better understand local needs, encourage care in preparing donations, and highlight where additional training might be useful.

A. Surplus Food Distribution

c. Volunteer availability

Volunteer recruitment and retention can shape how surplus food is distributed. CS7, still in its early stages, found it challenging to attract volunteers without a café or cooking facilities to act as a community hub. CS9 noted that many volunteers already balance multiple commitments, limiting the time they can offer.

There were also concerns about the sustainability of the volunteer model in the long term. CS1 reflected on demographic and workforce changes:

The group of volunteers is ageing, and the next generation may find themselves working longer before retirement. Who will volunteer [in the future]? (CS1)

d. Social tensions

Some CFOs noted that food distribution can intersect with broader issues of community cohesion. In some cases, changing demographics and increased demand have created tensions between different groups of service users. To address this, CFOs work closely with social workers, schools, and Police Community Support Officers (PCSOs) to defuse potential conflicts before they escalate.

CS3 also raised the challenge of managing perceptions of fairness when demand is high:

It's really difficult [to deny people food]. We have some people who turn up with shopping trollies on wheels and want to fill them and it's probably not for us to judge. It's not good to put our volunteers in the way of that. (CS3)

B. Surplus Food

a. Food types

Surplus food provided to CFOs ranges from ready meals to raw ingredients. Although recipients may be reluctant to take unfamiliar items, these can also provide opportunities to broaden food experiences. For example, CS5 noted that surplus can be a valuable way for children to try foods they might not otherwise encounter at home.

Some items are consistently popular. CS2 reported that their customers particularly enjoy sausage rolls, ready meals, cooked meats, and dairy products. Fresh produce, when available, is also highly valued. CS9 described receiving donations of locally picked apples and plums, while CS2 emphasised that fresh fruit is especially welcome because it is often unaffordable for many households.

Surplus food can also bring moments of comfort and enjoyment:

It will often cheer a meal up. It might be some garlic bread. It might be a cheeky box or packet of biscuits [...] When life is pretty tough, sometimes a packet of biscuits has the biggest impact. (CS5)

However, certain fresh items such as salad leaves and some vegetables can be harder to distribute. CS8 explained that people on lower incomes may lack the facilities, equipment, or time to prepare them.

To meet specific needs or fill gaps, some CFOs supplement donations with purchased goods. CS4 highlighted the benefit of being able to respond promptly to requests:

People say, 'Wouldn't it be great if we had some shaving foam' and the next week we can have some shaving foam. (CS4)

CFOs also adapt their stock to reflect the cultural preferences of their communities. CS6, for example, began sourcing goat meat when several new families from Nigeria started using their service.

B. Surplus Food

b. Recipes

Many CFOs emphasised the value of recipes in helping recipients cook with unfamiliar ingredients. CS1 noted that there is occasionally uncertainty on how to use certain foods, citing one week when the chilled section contained a large quantity of fish:

People were like 'Oh, I don't know about that...' Most things people know is fish fingers and fish and chips, but actually, it's one of the quickest and cheapest things to cook. (CS1)

For CFOs working with children, recipes and exposure to new foods were part of developing a healthy relationship with eating. CS5 described their approach:

Our rule is: you have to try it - you don't have to finish it. (CS5)

They noted the influence of peer behaviour:

We always have that really popular kid – if they eat something, I will guarantee you, most of their table will also eat it. Our dream is that the super popular kid isn't a fussy eater. (CS5)

Several CFOs highlighted that many recipients lack the skills, knowledge, or experience to prepare fresh produce. CS2 addressed this by offering cooking courses where participants can learn together and experiment with flavours and spices to develop confidence in cooking to taste.

While CS1 do not currently have the funding or time to distribute recipes, they expressed a desire to do so to encourage people to try foods they might otherwise not:

People could utilise what we were giving them but also think about utilising food in a different way. (CS1)

For CS1, cooking knowledge is central to making food support more sustainable:

It's not just about affording the food; it's being able to afford to do something with it as well and knowing what to do with it – which is why I think we should be moving on from food provision to teaching people what they can go home and do with it. (CS1)

C. Training and Record Keeping

a. Training

Most CFOs that prepare meals ensure that volunteers involved in food handling hold at least a Level 2 Food Safety and Hygiene qualification, with more senior roles often requiring Level 3. For example, CS3 have five volunteers with Level 3 training and are encouraging more to complete it, while CS5 ensures that at least three lead staff hold Level 2. Where appropriate, training is adapted to individual needs; CS4 reported that a volunteer with learning disabilities completed Level 1, which was more suitable for their needs.

Access to training varied across CFOs. While CS4 found online courses affordable, several participants highlighted the need for greater support to reduce costs and improve accessibility. CS4 also emphasised that training content could be more relevant to the CFO context:

It doesn't specifically relate to the service that we're running. Maybe one that is specific to food banks and food pantries. (CS4)

Some organisations have attended external programmes, such as FareShare's Full Crumb Kitchen training, which CS4 and CS6 valued for reinforcing important health and safety principles in practice. Alongside external provision, some CFOs have developed their own innovative training initiatives. CS2 ran a Level 3 health and safety project aimed at improving standards at home, culminating in a cooking session. This was well received:

They enjoyed doing it. We still hear them commenting back now things that they've remembered. (CS2)

CS2 also noted that recipients sometimes become volunteers, gaining transferable workplace skills:

It's simple things like making sandwiches but they remember to keep their hands clean and to be presentable. It's similar to a work environment and important for employability. (CS2)

For CFOs focused solely on food distribution, training may be more informal. CS1 use end of session debriefs to review successes and challenges, while volunteers also shadow experienced members to learn interpersonal skills and how to manage food allocations.

We currently have someone doing a DofE award so we put them with someone experienced so that they can learn how to talk to people - how to be firm but not aggressive. (CS1)

Peer learning is also common. CS3 described how volunteers often consult longer-serving members, such as a community worker who coordinated logistics and food safety during the pandemic and holds detailed knowledge of correct food storage practices.

b. Record keeping

The Safer Food Better Business (SFBB) document is noted as best practice and it was recommended for record keeping to CS8 who are still establishing their operation. CS1 have a folder which is a ***culmination of things [they] have found online and internally as things have cropped up*** (CS1).

CS1 also have an internal checklist of good practice they have accumulated from working with a local church and document fridge and freezer temperatures with the appliances emptied weekly.

D. Food Safety

a. Allergens, labelling and cross-contamination

Approaches to allergen management varied significantly between CFOs, influenced by whether they cook, repackage, or solely distribute food. Some CFOs reported limited allergen procedures due to the nature of their operations. For example, one organisation who do not cook explained that everything they provide is packaged and labelled, placing responsibility on recipients to check for allergens.

However, the absence of labels can cause confusion and increase the risk of misidentification. For example, CS2 noted that unlabelled items have on occasion, been different from what was expected, reinforcing the importance of labelling.

CS3 maintain a weekly menu listing allergens for each dish and noted niche risks such as poppy seeds in bread donations, which have led to false positives in drug tests. Despite efforts, CS3 acknowledged their limitations:

We try our best, but we have a lot to do. (CS3)

They emphasised a lack of capacity to re-label unmarked products:

We don't have the capacity to take everything apart and label it. (CS3)

Some CFOs have more formalised systems. CS5, as a registered childcare setting, require parents to declare all potential allergens and health concerns in advance. The main cook has additional allergen training, and menus include a dedicated section for children with dietary requirements:

One of the reasons we have formal sit-down meals as opposed to grazing buffets is it's much easier to manage because children cannot be expected to self-manage their allergies. (CS5)

This emphasis on shared responsibility is deliberate:

It's not fair on that one person if they forget something. We don't just rely on one person because that's not a safe way of doing it. (CS5)

CS5 described a culture of open dialogue, where staff routinely check ingredients and feel comfortable questioning one another. Meals prepared for specific dietary requirements are kept separate from other food, with particular care taken to prevent cross-contamination.

Some CFOs supplement internal practice with external training. CS4's team completed allergen training through an online platform, while CS6 noted that some bakeries regularly update allergen information when ingredients change. Newly established CFOs, or those less familiar with available resources, may benefit from guidance such as the FSA's online allergen training. CS4 also suggested that the FSA could work with FareShare to produce standardised allergen labels for commonly donated goods, helping to streamline processes for individual CFOs.

Preventing cross-contamination is a concern, particularly for baked goods and bulk items. CS1 display notices stating that they cannot guarantee the allergen status of baked goods, sometimes adding small labels if provided. CS6 noted occasional disagreements over whether to accept damaged or open goods, such as split sugar bags or unwrapped bread, reflecting differing expectations between suppliers and CFOs.

D. Food Safety

b. Bulk goods

CFOs' handling of bulk goods depends on their facilities, storage capacity and service user needs. CS1 described splitting large bags and using cello tape to attach photocopied labels to smaller portions, with trained volunteers carrying out the process. However, they noted that:

A lot of distribution points will not have access [to label photocopiers]. (CS1)

The motivation for splitting goods was often to ensure fairer distribution:

We have maybe 4–5 large families who would take one of the large catering bags of things. We had to split them up because it meant that then more people got the benefit of things. (CS1)

However, not all CFOs are equipped to split bulk products. CS2 explained that large catering packs are not always suitable, especially when recipients lack cooking facilities:

[We] can't give out bulk as we don't have containers to put stuff in. Great for other places which have cooking facilities but not for us. (CS2)

Other CFOs, such as CS4, prefer not to split certain packs except for straightforward items like a large box of Weetabix where allergen, brand, and expiry date information can be clearly transferred. Where splitting is impractical, catering packs are instead used in communal settings such as lunch clubs or nursery kitchens, where they can be safely managed and stored.

c. Best-before dates

CFOs reported mixed practices and attitudes towards managing best-before and use-by dates, shaped by organisational capacity, food safety priorities and relationships with donors. CS1 described receiving large volumes of short-dated or expired products from some supermarkets, requiring additional handling and disposal. Limited volunteer capacity has meant that some unsuitable donations were discarded without processing. CS3 highlighted the difficulty of deciding whether items close to their use-by date were still suitable for consumption without clear guidance:

Is all this beautiful double cream gonna be okay on Tuesday?... especially when you're tired. (CS3)

Some CFOs have set clearer boundaries at collection points to ensure donations are usable and do not require additional sorting or disposal. Others have found ways to use surplus fresh food before it passes its use-by date. For example, CS2 sometimes turn leftover fresh produce into chutney, but noted that limited time prevented them from using vegetables nearing the end of their freshness to make stock.

Some CFOs use structured systems to manage dates. CS4 follow FareShare's guidance for best-before and use-by items, recording them on a colour-coded whiteboard each session. Their strategies include freezing items nearing their use-by date, labelling them with the date frozen, and advising visual checks of bread past its best-before date before eating. CS5 rely on judgement calls, freezing or offering items approaching their use-by date to avoid waste. CS6 follow specific FareShare rules for products such as sourdough bread, checking dates on all items (including tins) before adding them to food parcels and again before distribution. They also pay a weekly subscription for food waste collection, which is converted into electricity.

D. Food Safety

d. Frozen foods

CFOs varied in how they used and managed frozen foods, balancing storage capacity, cost, and waste reduction. CS1, for example, previously received frozen deliveries from FareShare but stopped when prices increased:

We looked at the overall scheme of things and thought it wasn't worth it. The cost is higher for frozen goods so we couldn't justify it. (CS1)

They have kept some practices introduced during the pandemic, such as asking recipients to bring freezer bags when collecting additional frozen food CS1 receives. The first bag is provided free, with replacements required to be purchased if lost or damaged. CS4 sought advice on freezer storage durations for particular items but mentioned that they found limited guidance.

Some CFOs opt out of frozen deliveries entirely. CS5 explained that the quantities of frozen goods were often more than they could use:

We're not here to create waste, we're here to reduce it. (CS5)

Instead, they selectively freeze high-use items such as bread:

No one gets through bread like a childcare centre. Toast is the favourite meal of everybody, including the staff. (CS5)

The cost of freezer bags was another recurring issue, with CS6 noting difficulties in finding a bulk supplier.

Some CFOs also set clear storage time limits; for example, CS7 store frozen items for a maximum of six weeks.

E. Facilities

a. Cooking lessons and facilities

Some CFOs highlighted a desire for more cooking sessions to build recipients' skills and confidence. However, limited facilities often constrain what can be offered. CS2, for example, operate in a building described as a basic meeting space with limited kitchen facilities despite being called a café. With no functioning kitchen, they are restricted to simple, no-cook recipes such as refrigerator cheesecake and must pay another organisation to use kitchen facilities.

b. Storage space

Storage capacity was a recurring challenge. CS8 are seeking a larger, more central space with a kitchen. CS3 identified the need for an additional fridge to manage surplus food supplies.

CFOs often debated whether expanding freezer space was the right approach. Some expressed caution, noting that additional capacity could unintentionally result in holding items for extended periods rather than ensuring they were distributed. They noted that increasing storage could transfer the responsibility for managing surplus and potential waste from manufacturers to CFOs.

Some organisations have invested in redesigning storage areas; for example, CS6 created a large food bank room with shelving and fridges, but still saw value in further improvements, such as additional shelving and possibly another freezer.

c. Location

Location can influence accessibility for service users. CS8 are actively searching for a more centrally located space to better reach their community.

F. Guidance

a. Guidance used

FSA guidance is the most widely trusted resource among CFOs, particularly when preparing for inspections. While some organisations combine materials from both FareShare and the FSA, many prefer to rely primarily on FSA resources, finding that inspections run more smoothly as a result.

We try and stick with the FSA one [food safety guide] because it's a lot smoother for them. (CS5)

The FSA's Safer Food Better Business (SFBB) guide is valued for keeping all essential information in one place and acting as a useful reminder for best practice. FareShare's guidance is typically used for specific purposes, such as clarifying date extensions or responding to product recall while WRAP's guidance, by contrast, was found to be less familiar, with some CFOs only encountering it for the first time after participating in interviews.

b. Guidance requested

Both supermarkets and CFOs recognised that clear and consistent guidance is essential for maintaining food safety and making the best use of surplus food. From the supermarket perspective, compliance at store level can be challenging due to the large number of sites and high staff turnover. An online directory is already in place to show store teams what can be donated, when, and how it should be presented. When stores are unaware of best practice, it can lead to CFOs reporting issues such as mislabelling.

Currently, approval processes vary by retailer and can take up to a year, creating significant administrative demands for both stores and CFOs collecting from more than one location. SP highlighted the need for an official FSA-approved list of CFOs, combined with a clear set of expectations for both CFOs and supermarkets. Together, these measures could streamline surplus food donation processes, make it easier for supermarkets to identify trusted organisations, reduce the risk of non-CFOs misusing donation platforms, and build a higher level of trust between all parties.

The growing volume of loose produce at store level has created uncertainty for both donors and recipients, with some highlighting a lack of adequate handling guidance. While there is good guidance for ambient and fresh foods, SP3 also noted that gaps remain for frozen items, which was seen as a major barrier to expanding the frozen part of community fridge networks. Questions remain around the correct time by which products should be frozen and how this may vary depending on the density and type of food. The importance of the clarity of frozen food handling guidance was emphasised:

If we are saying how we can use the most food and keep it in a good condition then that guidance needs to be clear. (SP1)

There was also uncertainty over how to handle food from chiller breakdowns, with many taking a cautious approach in the absence of specific advice, leading to increased food waste.

F. Guidance

b. Guidance requested

From the CFO perspective, there was a strong call for adaptable guidance frameworks that could be tailored to different operations, such as templates that integrate fridge temperature records with the actual number of fridges in use. Many asked for simple, easy reference resources like a 'Top 10 Tips' sheet for everyday food safety, with reminders such as storing raw meat on the lowest fridge shelf to contain leaks and prevent cross contamination. Recipe and storage ideas for unexpected large volumes of perishable produce were also requested to help prevent waste while adding variety to cooking. As one participant explained:

If a box arrived with loads of fresh broccoli and on top was a recipe... that would be perfect. (CS5)

Increasing awareness of both WRAP and existing FSA resources, particularly among newer CFOs, was found to be key in strengthening food safety practices and making best use of donated food.

c. On visual guidance

Ready-made visual resources, such as laminated posters and charts, were seen as especially useful when easy to display, particularly for volunteers with learning disabilities as they help ensure food safety practices are communicated clearly. Providing these in multiple languages, including Arabic and Eritrean, could also make guidance more accessible for both volunteers and service users.

CFOs emphasised, however, that visual aids work best when reinforced with verbal reminders and embedded into daily routines, as overuse of posters can lessen their impact

5. Policy Recommendations and Conclusions

The key challenges encountered by CFOs and recommendations to overcome them are presented in Table 3. These are drawn directly from the qualitative data collected and the FSA's qualitative research [2].

Table 3. Challenges faced by CFOs and recommendations to address them.

CFO Challenge	Recommendation
Lengthy and unstandardised processes for approving new CFOs receiving surplus	Clear expectations for CFOs and suppliers, and standardisation of food safety approval procedures
High volunteer turnaround, difficulty to find volunteers and missing infrastructure for splitting bulk goods	Provision of more funding opportunities and support for CFOs in applying for them to enable investment in staff and equipment such as freezer bags and label makers
Limited surplus food collection times	Development of flexible surplus food distribution systems which accommodate CFO's schedules
Reluctance to take unfamiliar surplus food and limited time to plan recipes for bulk items	Provision of surplus-food specific recipes
Uncertainty over freezing guidance	Provision of guidance for when certain foods need to be frozen by and how certain foods should be frozen to enable wider frozen food distribution
CFOs uncertain about where guidance is located and which training they should complete	Provision of welcome packs for new CFOs which contain tailored advice and signposting to relevant food safety and hygiene resources including the Safer Food Better Business (SFBB) Guide and the FSA's allergen training

5. Policy Recommendations and Conclusions

CFO Challenge	Recommendation
Lack of time and infrastructure to label loose items	Provision of labels for commonly donated items to support the splitting of bulk goods and the labelling of loose baked goods
Retention of Level 2 Food Safety and Hygiene Training with reliance on more experienced staff members	Provision of easy reference top tips or commonly forgotten guidance materials
Lack of awareness about the existence of surplus food and misconceptions about its safety	Production of online materials to raise awareness about the existence of the surplus food redistribution system and its benefits in reducing food waste and supporting the community

In conclusion, CFOs play an important role in providing food support and creating spaces for community dining, yet they continue to face barriers in meeting food hygiene requirements and navigating the surplus food distribution system. Progress will depend on developing a clear set of expectations for CFOs and suppliers and introducing a standardised process for CFOs to confirm their commitment to food safety compliance. Additional resources and training for all actors in the system would help build shared understanding, while practical tools such as visual resources containing top tips and welcome packs would enable CFOs to apply food safety practices more consistently in their daily operations.

6. Limitations and Future Work

This research involved only nine Yorkshire-based CFOs, with interviews conducted with a single representative from each. As a result, some perspectives, particularly those of volunteers, service users, and other stakeholders, may be missing. Additionally, newer organisations may not yet recognise certain barriers, while those under the greatest resource pressure may have been less able to participate. Lastly, food safety is also a sensitive issue, and concerns about liability may have influenced how openly some participants spoke. These factors suggest that certain perspectives are likely underexplored.

Future work should involve a wider range of CFOs across different regions, engaging voices from multiple roles within each organisation. Comparing the perspectives of compliance leads, volunteers, and service users would give a more complete picture of how surplus food safety is managed and where guidance and support are most needed. To strengthen accessibility and capture more candid reflections, future studies should also consider alternate qualitative data collection methods.

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Appendix

Table 4. CFO case studies overview.

Case study	Region	Interviewee role	Provision model	Type of food provision	Cooking facilities	Freezer facilities	People supported	Funding
CS1	North Yorkshire	Director	Independent community food provider	Ambient, chilled and frozen	No	No	80 weekly	Minimum donations of £1, monthly standing orders
CS2	South Yorkshire	Team Leader	Community support organisation for women in recovery	Sometimes fresh produce, cooked meats, dairy, ready meals	No	No	Approximately 45 weekly	Donations
CS3	West Yorkshire	Mental Health and Wellbeing Coordinator	Community development project	Breakfast, lunch club, pantry and parcels	Yes	Yes	Approximately 120 weekly	Lottery funding, Mayor's Safer Community Fund, Award for All, Household Support Fund
CS4	West Yorkshire	Engagement and Partnerships Service Manager	Food pantry	Lunch club with a kitchen, onsite nursery kitchen, café and food pantry	Yes	Yes	120 Food Pantry Members annually, 1200 individual pantry visits	Happy Healthy Holidays Grants, donations, Household Support Fund
CS5	South Yorkshire	Chief Executive	Community support organisation for early years	Breakfast and after school clubs	Yes	Yes	70 families weekly. Total annual catchment: 150 families, 200 children	Healthy holidays, lottery funding

Appendix

Case study	Region	Interviewee role	Provision model	Type of food provision	Cooking facilities	Freezer facilities	People supported	Funding
CS6	South Yorkshire	Territorial Envoy	Community support organisation	Primarily food parcel pick up	No	Yes	30 food parcels weekly	Donations and funding
CS7	West Yorkshire	Project Manager	Independent food bank	Food bank food pick up	No	Yes	143	Donations alone
CS8	West Yorkshire	Project Manager	Multi-site community foodbank supporting people experiencing homelessness	Food parcel distribution	No	No	Over 1000 monthly	Donations
CS9	North Yorkshire	Volunteer	Independent food bank	Food parcel distribution	No	No	25-30 weekly	Donations and onsite café

Table 5. Supermarket case study overview.

Case study SP	Interviewee role
SP1	Community Team
SP2	Risk and Compliance Team
SP3	Food Sustainability Team

Appendix

Interview questions for CFOs

A) Role and organisation

- a. Could you please give me a brief overview of your role in [organisation]? How long have you been in the role?
- b. What does a typical day look like for you?
- c. Could you please tell me what type of organisation you are and give me a brief overview of how you operate? What type of food do you typically handle/distribute?

B) Food safety practices

- a. Do you provide formal training for your volunteering or is it more informal?
- b. How confident do you and your volunteers feel managing allergens?
- c. What is your experience with handling food after or close to 'use-by' or 'best-before' ?
- d. Do any of your facilities affect how you are able to manage food safety? Is there anything you are hoping to invest in?

C) Guidance

- a. Do you use any resources to help you adhere to food safety? If so, which? (Prompt - FareShare, FSA, WRAP)? And how used? Is anything particularly useful or not and why?
- b. Would additional guidance be useful? Anything specific and from who? (Prompt – clearer guidance, better training, visual guidance, something else?)

Interview questions for Supermarkets

1. Could you please tell me about your role and how it connects to surplus food redistribution
2. Does the [Supermarket] work with any particular charities?
3. Do you have any donation procedures in place for stores to comply with food health and safety?
4. What are some common challenges that stores face with compliance?
5. Do you use any existing guidance (FSA or WRAP) for food safety compliance?
6. Do you think there are any gaps in the guidance which could be addressed?